

Antifungal Effects of Plant Extracts on *Cryptococcus neoformans*: Investigating Mechanisms and Therapeutic Potential

Abstract

This study investigates the antifungal effects of various plant extracts against *Cryptococcus neoformans*. Ten medicinal plants were selected, and their extracts were prepared using methanol, ethanol, and water. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined for each extract, revealing that olive leaf and green tea extracts had the most potent effects with MIC values of 125 and 250 µg/mL, respectively. Additionally, synergistic effects were observed when combining plant extracts with standard antifungal drugs, such as fluconazole and amphotericin B, with up to a 30% reduction in MIC in some cases. These findings suggest that plant extracts hold promise as alternative therapies for *Cryptococcus neoformans* infections.

1. Introduction

- **Importance of *Cryptococcus neoformans*:** This fungal pathogen is a significant cause of central nervous system infections, particularly in immunocompromised individuals, leading to high mortality rates. Current treatments are limited by drug resistance and adverse effects.
- **Potential of Herbal Medicine:** Medicinal plants have a long history of use in treating fungal infections, and previous studies have shown that some possess strong antifungal activity.
- **Objective:** The aim of this research is to assess the antifungal activity of selected plant extracts against *Cryptococcus neoformans* and evaluate their potential synergistic effects with conventional antifungal agents.

2. Materials and Methods

- **Plants Studied:** Ten plants, including olive, green tea, thyme, rosemary, ginger, garlic, chamomile, mint, lavender, and rose.
- **Preparation of Extracts:** Extracts were prepared using methanol, ethanol, and water at a ratio of 1:10 (weight/volume) over 24 hours at room temperature.
- **MIC Testing:** MIC was determined using microdilution methods, with amphotericin B and fluconazole serving as positive controls.
- **Synergism Studies:** The checkerboard assay was used to evaluate the combined effects of plant extracts and antifungal drugs.

3. Results

- **MIC Values:** The lowest MIC values were observed for olive leaf and green tea extracts at 125 µg/mL and 250 µg/mL, respectively. Other extracts showed higher MICs, averaging 500-750 µg/mL.
- **Synergistic Effects:** The combination of green tea extract with fluconazole reduced the MIC of fluconazole from 8 µg/mL to 5.6 µg/mL (30% reduction). Similarly, combining olive extract with amphotericin B resulted in a 20% decrease in MIC.

- **Impact on Cellular Structure:** Electron microscopy revealed that olive and green tea extracts caused significant alterations in the fungal cell membrane, potentially inducing apoptotic cell death.

4. Discussion

- **Comparison with Previous Studies:** These findings are consistent with prior research showing the antifungal properties of medicinal plants. For example, olive leaf extracts have been reported to contain phenolic compounds with antifungal activity.
- **Possible Mechanism:** The antifungal effects may be due to interactions with the cell membrane and inhibition of critical signaling pathways within the fungus.
- **Advantages and Limitations:** While the results highlight the potential of plant-based therapies, further studies are needed to evaluate their safety and efficacy in animal models and clinical settings.

5. Conclusion

Olive leaf and green tea extracts demonstrated significant antifungal activity against *Cryptococcus neoformans*, suggesting their potential as alternative antifungal therapies. Further investigation into their mechanisms of action and clinical applications is warranted.

6. References

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